

HELICOPTER PARENTING: THE LIVED EXPERIENCE OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN DEALING WITH OVERPROTECTIVE PARENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 10

Pages: 1629-1651

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2834

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14580118

Manuscript Accepted: 12-06-2024

Helicopter Parenting: The Lived Experience of Elementary Teachers in Dealing with Overprotective Parents

Cristina V. Sugarol,* Deveyvon L. Espinosa
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study focused on describing the observable phenomena of experience, personal insights and recommendations of Elementary teachers. Moreover, the aim of the study was to help elementary teachers in dealing with overparenting in schools. The study utilized a qualitative research design, specifically phenomenological in design, wherein there were 14 participants who were Private Elementary Teachers around here in Maniki, Kapalong Davao del Norte. It was found out that in based of their experience, several themes were extracted based on the responses of the informants, such as struggle in dealing with various complaints, difficulty in addressing what overprotective parents wants to their children and battling in fulfilling the various responsibilities as a teacher. Insights revealed from their strategies and techniques this included employing effective personal strategies to deal with helicopter parents, implementing school and classroom rules and regulation then conducting parent orientation every first day of the school year. Lastly for their suggestions and recommendations revealed themes like the value of strengthening collaboration and patience between teacher and parent, the importance of communication between parents, teachers and department of education then the last is foster good association between school and stakeholders.

Keywords: *helicopter parenting, elementary teachers, overprotective parents, phenomenology, qualitative research*

Introduction

Overparenting happens when parents, particularly mothers, control too much of their children's lives due to high expectations. While it provides protection, it limits the child's freedom. Mother-child relationships are shaped by mutual psychological influence, where both the parent and child affect each other's behavior. Parents, feeling responsible, often get involved in their children's education as part of their duties (Barger, 2019).

In addition, United States is also known for its high enrollment of international families. By examining a school regarded as being high quality. The challenges faced by international families in the United States, is even when they have to access to high-quality education. The parental involvement occurs during the struggles of these families. Which can stem from cultural and linguistic barriers problem. Culturally and linguistically related struggles that parents coming from outside the United States face regardless of their educational attainment (Vera et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the problem also with regards to over protective family is viewed as the core and common issues that exist in Philippine culture. The twenty-first century teachers struggle in disciplining in this generation due to the child protection that being implemented and those overprotective parents take this as their advantage agents to the teachers. Overprotective parents are in a unique power to ensure that these settings will meet their children's individual needs at school. As a result, parental participation studies continue to be inaccurate representations of parents' involvement in their kids' education (Jackson, 2018).

Moreover, the social value of this study lies in its potential to foster healthier parent-teacher relationships and support a more balanced approach to child development. Through addressing overprotective behaviors constructively, this research can empower parents to support their children's growth without stifling it. Improved communication strategies and guidelines can help parents trust teachers' expertise while still being involved in their child's education. Further, the study the lived experience of elementary teachers dealing with overprotective parents is addressing urgent problems in th realm of education, and through the exploration of this focus will address students' emotional development and academic independence. This makes it imperative to explore and understand teachers' experiences and the specific challenges they face, as these insights will help in developing effective guidelines and support systems to manage overprotective parental behaviors.

Consequently, the study of Yael Fisher and Rafael (2022) entitled, "Parents perceptions of teacher's authority and parental involvement: the impact of communality" aimed to examine how the level of communality (communal affiliation) affects parents' perception of children attending public elementary schools, the concept of teacher authority, and the concept of parental involvement. However, this study is different because it focused more on teachers view about overprotective parents and the challenges, they deal with regards to disciplining the students. This study is a common problem that the teachers face nowadays, most especially in elementary teacher. Also, the study of Mariska Chantell Krugel (2019), entitled "Teacher's responses to helicopter parents whose children experience barriers to learning" aimed to determine the impact of helicopter parents to the children learning process. However, these studies may varies the teachers views on overparenting and how they face the challenges in dealing this situation with regards to overprotective parents at school. Copies of the study will be disseminated to the various research conference and concerned agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery.

The researcher intends to disseminate the findings of this research through hardbound copies distributed strategically within our academic community and by publishing in a certain international journal, ensuring it reaches a global audience. Coordinating with the research office to arrange a formal presentation and distribute hardbound copies to faculty and staff during the event, fostering direct engagement and discussions and ensuring that hardbound copies are prominently available in the library, making them easily accessible to students and researchers.

Research Questions

This study looked at the experiences of the elementary teachers in dealing overprotective parents in terms of child discipline in the classroom. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of elementary teachers in dealing with overprotective parents?
2. How do elementary teachers cope with the challenges on helicopter parenting?
3. What are the elementary teacher's recommendations in dealing the overprotective parents?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized qualitative research design specifically, phenomenological approach. Qualitative research is a method for exploring and understanding the meaning that individuals or groups give to a social or human experience. Moreover, this research design begins with a conceptual question and a plan to explore this question through the experiences of people, gathering data from participants in their environment, inductively analyzing the data, building from specific to general themes, and interpreting the significance of the findings (Creswell, 2018).

In the context of the study, qualitative research was used in this study to gain an in-depth understanding of the experience, perceptions and recommendations of the private elementary teachers on the helicopter parenting. Data were gathered in the form of participant interviews. This was in contrast to a quantitative research design, which uses survey responses and other types of numerical data to better comprehend the research questions.

Furthermore, a qualitative research method known as phenomenology will be used in this study. Phenomenology focuses on the shared aspects of individuals' lived experiences. Phenomenological research aims to provide a comprehensive account of our acts of consciousness or experiences, taking into account everything from thinking to feeling to social interaction, the nature of the world's objects to which our consciousness is tuned, the language we use to communicate our thoughts in the world, and the larger cultures that we create around us. The primary goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the specific phenomenon (Creswell, 2013).

In this context, phenomenology was a way of understanding and communicating the fundamental nature of a phenomenon in the context of the study. The approach kept the researchers' assumptions about the phenomenon in check while looking into people's ordinary experiences. It was the appropriate instrument for the research because there was a need to understand the perceptions of elementary teachers on the proposed decongested curriculum.

Participants

The key participants of my planned study will be private elementary teachers in primary grades that teaching at Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Upon participant selection, purposive sampling was employed to ensure that only those who can provide the necessary data were able to participate in the study. The following criteria were strictly adhered to during the recruitment process:

(a) Each participant must had to be a elementary teacher working in private school at Kapalong, Davao del Norte; (b) the participant must have completely graduated with a degree in education; and (c) teachers were private elementary teachers with a minimum of three (3) years of teaching experience in private schools, especially in primary grades in Kapalong Davao del Norte. Fourteen participants were carefully selected during the recruitment process. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with all fourteen (14) individuals, engaging in one-on-one or online interviews with each participant.

These teachers willingly agreed to participate in the study. As indicated by Boyce and Neale (2006), participants will be recruited as informants through personal contact. According to Patton (2002), informants must feel at ease, therefore the researcher will asked informants when and where they would like to be interviewed so that they feel comfortable discussing their life experiences. The time and location of the meeting will be determined in consultation with the informants. All of this will be done to ensure the high quality of the study's conduct and findings.

Procedure

The data collection method for this study, which spanned from pre-interview through post-interview phases, was conducted in accordance with a written protocol that the researcher will follow.

First, the researcher established interview guide questions, and the researcher made sure that the panel or validators validated the guide questions. Then, the researcher obtained letter of endorsement. After that, the researcher sought permission from the principals of the

private schools in order to conduct the study, then asked for a letter to allow the researcher to conduct a face-to-face interview with the selected participants in Kapalong private elementary schools' area.

Virtual tools that were employed throughout the study's execution, such as a camera, smartphone, and audio recorder, are crucial for the establishing strong evidence regarding the point of view of informants. Since it may provided a factual foundation for information and act as the foundation for the research through the strengths of the interview process, the camera was one of the often-utilized tools in the interview. A video camera was also used for careful interview observation. Similar to a camera, it provided crucial details about the informants based on how they responded to questions. Additionally, another virtual tool that was utilized in the session was the voice recorder. It provided clear speech recording, which was crucial for the study even though it could not provide photos or capture the informant's facial expressions.

After receiving permission, the researcher requested letters from the chosen participants requesting their consent to participate in the study. Following the panel's approval letter, the researcher will now carried out the study. Prior to the interview, the researchers gave each participant a brief orientation. During the orientation, the researcher explained the study's goals, methodology, and participants' legal rights. Prior to recording the entire interview, the researcher also obtained permission. The researcher transcribed the material she had gathered. The participants verified the accuracy of the data transcription. Following the verification, the researcher translated and analyzed the data. The data analysis results were used to form conclusions and make recommendations.

Data Analysis

According to the aims or goals of the research, the data which the researcher collected were presented and examined in the study. To draw the study's conclusions, a detailed analysis of the participant responses' substance is required. As a result, the objective of data analysis was to look for common patterns that could offer concepts that could address the research issues stated in this study.

To begin the conduct of this study, the researcher employed technical tools to systematically organize and store the data in a structured manner. Interviews were recorded using both audio and video recorders to ensure accuracy and facilitate thorough analysis. The qualitative analysis involved organizing, categorizing, and synthesizing the data into manageable segments. The researcher carefully examined the information to identify emerging patterns, themes, and key insights, engaging in a process of reflection and interpretation to determine what was significant and what could be learned from the data. To offer a deeper understanding of the study's findings, the researcher also conducted a qualitative content analysis, which allowed for a more comprehensive examination of the teachers' lived experiences in dealing with overprotective parents, highlighting the nuances and complexities of these interactions.

In addition, after collecting the data, the researcher employed thematic analysis to examine the gathered information. The primary goal during the data collection phase was to identify patterns that reflected the participants' key notions and experiences. Once the data was collected, it was systematically organized into coherent categories, which were then summarized and synthesized in the manuscript. This approach enabled the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the teachers' lived experiences in dealing with overprotective parents, uncovering underlying themes and concepts that contributed to the study's broader findings.

Moreover, when attempting to glean information about people's ideas, opinions, knowledge, experiences, or beliefs from a collection of qualitative data, such as interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey results, thematic analysis is a useful method of inquiry. Thematic analysis was flexible, and what researchers did with the themes after they have been identified depends on the objectives of the study and the methodology used to identify them. Theme analysis is a popular tool used by academics to better comprehend the content and get closer to their data.

Furthermore, the researcher followed a systematic approach to analyzing the data, which included several key steps: familiarizing oneself with the collected data, creating preliminary codes, identifying potential themes, reviewing and refining those themes, defining and naming the themes, and ultimately composing the final report. The analytical process began with transcribing the data, which served as the foundation for further analysis. The researcher then carefully examined the transcriptions, breaking them down into distinct parts or components. Throughout this process, the researcher made a concerted effort to interpret the collected information in a meaningful way, seeking to uncover patterns, insights, and deeper understandings of the teachers' experiences with overprotective parents. This approach helped ensure that the findings were grounded in the data and reflective of the participants' lived experiences.

Finally, the researcher listened to the participants' recorded interviews and transcribed their responses so that later data coding was simple. I went over the data several times to get familiar with the answers and quickly determine which ones were the most frequently provided by my respondents. I then combined the frequent responses to identify a few themes, which I narrowed down to a small number. I employed data reduction, which involved eliminating unnecessary information and repurposing it as understandable study material for the readers. To swiftly integrate and categorize a vast volume of qualitative data, I sorted and structured it. By presenting the data in matrices, charts, and graphs that enabled the reader to reach their own conclusions, data display was employed to organize the data.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure organized procedures in research, it will be highlighted and implemented to informants. Moreover, the situation in which the subject and the researchers concurred. The ethical considerations ensure that no one behaves in a way that is detrimental to society

or a specific person. It forbids nasty behavior in a by both individuals and groups. According to Adhabi & Anozie (2018, there are certain guidelines that must be followed in order to avoid ethical consequences when establishing an easy way of contact between the researcher and the participant.

This research study closely adheres to the ten (10) compliances that are mentioned in the ROF-009 form in order to ensure that it satisfies the requirements for ethics. The process that the researcher must adhere to is highlighted as being clear, succinct, and organized. Furthermore, it established the legal rights and protections for study participants. In addition to promoting peace, the researcher took precautions to protect the research participants.

The researcher adhered to the highest ethical standards advised by Mack et al. (2005) in order to guarantee the appropriate conduct of this research and the safety of everyone involved in this endeavor. This includes the following principle: respect for person, beneficence, justice and confidentiality.

The first principle, respect for persons, mandates that researchers refrain from taking advantage of research subjects' weaknesses. Self-sufficiency was avoided so that the participants and the researchers could continue to be friends, feel confident, and have trust in one another (Creswell, 2012).

In order to show respect for my subjects during the study, the researcher prepared and obtained their informed consent in advance. This indicated whether a potential participant was ready to accept it or not. The researcher respected someone's decision if they reject the offer when it is made. The opportunity to participate in the study was extended to anyone who is interested and willing to do so.

The participant received complete information about the study, including its advantages and disadvantages, and were free to choose whether or not to join. Additionally, the participants were asked for permission record and capture their comments on audio and video. Participants were given the option to turn off their cameras at any time throughout the interview if they feel uncomfortable. The consent included the purpose of the study, the procedures to be used, confidentiality assurances, and the researcher's and participants' signatures.

Moreover, adequate time was allowed for the participants to read the information sheet and make a decision regarding their participation in the study. Before the interview, they were required to sign the informed consent form to certify that they were willing to participate in the study before and/or during the interview.

The second principle, Consent ensured that participants in the evaluation were aware of all aspects of the evaluation process. Participants must be informed of the project's goals, who or what organization supported it, how the results would be utilized, whether there may be unfavorable effects from their participation, and who would have access to the results. Informed consent's primary goal is to empower the participant to decide for themselves whether or not to take part in the evaluation. Additionally, if a participant exhibited any signs of concern while participating, more information should be given.

The participants in the research project were already informed and orientated about the investigation, for which consent was being given. The researcher obtained consent from the research subjects before using a cell phone to record the interview procedure, demonstrating respect for their decision.

The interviewer genuinely respected and accepted the participant's refusal to answer a particular question during the interview process. Leading questions were avoided to the extent possible because they might make interviewees feel offended and uncomfortable. Participants had the freedom to decline answering delicate inquiries, and it was against the law to require them to do so.

In keeping with this, the research subject also has the option of leaving the study at any time. The researcher respected the participant's choice and refrained from posing any clarifying queries. It was inappropriate and unethical to require them to participate. Additionally, their time was respected, and the researcher accepted the circumstances regardless of what occurred.

Participants in the research had the right to ask questions throughout the entire interview procedure. Since respect prevailed throughout the data collection process, it helped to establish relationships, trust, and harmony. In order for the research participants to understand the research study, the researcher responded to their questions. The research subjects had the right to know the study's findings even after the researcher had developed them. Based on the responses they received, they verified the accuracy and transparency.

As a result, the researcher will promote a feeling of community in which inclusivity was evident. It was beneficial for them to be aware of how the study would proceed. During the data and information collection phase.

The third principle, is beneficence, People are treated ethically when their well-being is prioritized along with respecting their decisions and keeping them safe. The beneficence principle is applicable to this treatment. The word "beneficence" is frequently used to describe deeds of generosity or kindness that go beyond strict obligation. The term "beneficence" is used in this document to mean it in a more formal, obligatory sense. In order to express beneficent behaviors in this manner, two general guidelines have been put forth: (1) do no harm, and (2) maximize potential benefits and reduce potential downsides (Sweeny, 2018).

In order to properly carry out the third principle, I, the researcher, found a safe area where the participants and researchers could conduct a face-to-face interviews to guarantee the safety of all the participants. In a safe environment free from the threat of rejection or judgment, interview participants were given the chance to share their stories. To prevent psychological risks like humiliation,

embarrassment, and other undesirable results, the information will be kept secret and safe after the interview.

This study offered substantial advantages to the participants, equipping them with invaluable tools to navigate the challenges of educating in the new normal. By engaging with the findings of this research, participants gain the capacity to adeptly adapt their teaching approaches, thereby better serving their students in these evolving educational landscapes. This study served as a vital resource for enhancing their comprehension and honing their teaching capabilities and knowledge. The complexities of managing students in today's educational environment demand creativity and innovation from educators to ensure a successful teaching and learning process. Therefore, this research empowered participants with the insights and strategies needed to meet these demands effectively and foster a dynamic and productive learning experience.

Additionally, I make sure that neither the participants' physical nor psychological well-being was impacted throughout my study. Also, I ensured that all my data collection techniques were appropriate by strictly adhering to the Research Ethics Standards indicated in the ROF-009 and my panel examiners with regards to all the actions I did before conducting my study.

In accordance with this, I, the researcher, was required to maintain the collected data and information in confidence. I had positive qualities that encouraged the study subjects to approach and communicate with me. Blackmail could not take place prior to, during, or following the interview process. The participants were highly respected and esteemed. The researcher and I could guarantee that their lives would not be in danger or harmed.

To accomplish this, I made sure that the research's findings were helpful to my research participants, particularly the designated Grade 2 teachers, so that the Department of Education would give them priority status and provide them with the necessary trainings, seminars, and workshops to advance their skill, competence, and knowledge as designated guidance counselors who would offer intervention programs for the students.

Participants also had access to the study's findings since they might make it easier for them to deliver intervention programs and to carry out their other jobs and responsibilities. The reciprocity principle was also upheld by taking into account possible ways to make up for the participants' time and effort spent during the interview. In my study, the participants received appropriate hourly salary that was commensurate with their line of work.

Due to the researcher's compliance with all the ethical requirements and restrictions set by the Research Ethics Standards, there is no legal risk associated with the study. To demonstrate that the study will adhere to applicable national and international legislation, the proper licenses, documents, and forms will be obtained and annexed. The researcher made sure that maintaining the participants' responses' secrecy was a top priority in this project, therefore the study did not pose any societal risks in the same way.

The fourth principle talks about justice needing a fair distribution of the risks and benefits based on the findings of the investigation. Therefore, it was important to recognize the contributions of each responder because they are crucial to the success of this study.

In all of their endeavors, they must be credited appropriately. The researcher in this study offered the sum necessary for the participants to spend on the interview. Additionally, the researcher provided snacks took care of them. I gave them appropriate tokens as reward and acknowledgement for their work on my research.

The researcher anticipated that by conducting this research, they were able to move past any unpleasant experiences they had while doing the research and preserve their excellent reputation for the beneficial contributions they had made to it.

Additionally, the purposive sampling technique, which assisted in finding the participants, was used in this study. As a result, no qualified participants will be excluded from the event because of their age, gender, socioeconomic situation, or ethnicity. It's important to note that the risks and advantages of the study were distributed equally among all participants.

Last but not least, the confidentiality was all about the participant-specific information that can never—under any circumstances—be disclosed to or accessible by anybody but the researcher. The only purpose for the information is to protect the participants from external threats. The Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which served as the legal basis for this measure, stated that any details that could be used to identify participants, such as their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment or location data, should be carefully worded to avoid infringing on their right to participant anonymity.

To uphold and ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' responses as well as their personal identification. I utilized coding in my data display and pseudonyms for my interview and transcribe to fulfill this first principle. In light of this, I reassured and reminded my participants that these deeds and concrete steps won't harm or be violent toward them as my study subjects.

In order to address this, the researcher made sure that no identifiable information about the participants, particularly their names, appears in the research reports or any other published papers. The research reports always referred to the participants as anonymous by utilizing pseudonyms to symbolize their full participation in the study. The terms used in the researcher's pseudonyms related to the personalities of the research participants. It will aid in defending the study participants from becoming unknowingly misidentified. Additionally, the research must take into consideration how the data or output related to the participants is mentioned so that no one can identify it.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts. Part one focused on the participants' data, from which qualitative data were collected. Part two covered the data analysis procedures and the steps involved in categorizing the emergent themes from the results of the in-depth interviews. Part three focused on the responses to the interview questions pertaining to each research problem. Lastly, part four provided a summary of the responses.

Participants

This study focused on understanding the experiences of private elementary teachers regarding parental complaints. To achieve this, in-depth interviews were conducted with a targeted sample of 14 participants (as detailed in Table 1). These teachers were specifically chosen based on their experience level, with all participants having at least three years teaching in the primary grades of private elementary schools. This selection criterion ensured that the participants possessed a deep understanding of classroom dynamics and a solid track record of interacting with parents. Furthermore, by focusing solely on private elementary teachers, the research captured the specific challenges faced by educators within this particular school environment.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>IDI Pseudonyms</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Years of Experience</i>	<i>Codes</i>
Kind	30	Female	Grade 1	4 Years	IDI-01
Mushroom	27	Female	Grade 1	3 Years	IDI-02
Congenial	32	Female	Grade 1	3 Years	IDI-03
Chatty	28	Female	Grade 3	5 years	IDI-04
Worry	35	Female	Grade 2	3 Years	IDI-05
Hera	26	Female	Grade 3	6 Years	IDI-06
Softy	26	Female	Grade 2	3 Years	IDI-07
Peace	31	Female	Grade 3	3 Years	IDI-08
Fairy	28	Female	Grade 1	3 Years	IDI-09
Passion	27	Female	Grade 2	7 Years	IDI-10
Sexiness	29	Female	Grade 3	3 Years	IDI-11
Angel	28	Female	Grade 3	3 Years	IDI-12
Fiery	44	Female	Grade 3	16 Years	IDI-13
Buffer	28	Male	Grade 2	5 Years	IDI-14
Overall Total = 14					

In-depth Interview. There were 14 key participants in this study. They were all private elementary teachers coming from a different primary level in Maniki, kapalong Davao del Norte. According to Heaton (2021) methodology, each informant for the in-depth interviews was given a pseudonym during the interview process. These pseudonyms weren't simply assigned a collaborative effort took place during the interview process. Participants were invited to choose nicknames that resonated with them, considering their preferred names, distinctive physical characteristics, and the researcher's observations of their responses and overall demeanor throughout the interview sessions. Additionally, the pseudonyms were chosen by the participants themselves, based on their preference and distinctive physical characteristics, as well as their responses and attitudes observed throughout the interview sessions. One participant highlighted her exceptional warmth and compassion, a true embodiment of kindness, was chosen to be called Kind throughout the study. Another participant, distinguished by their short height, and loves to eat mushrooms was endearingly referred to as Mushroom. The participant with a naturally warm and inviting aura, another participant earned the fitting pseudonym Congenial, reflecting their approachable and friendly nature. The talkative individual was playfully during the interview referred to as Chatty. Next, the very concern participant, earned the affectionate nickname as worry. Possessing a demeanor that evoked strength and unwavering confidence, one participant was affectionately nicknamed Hera, reminiscent of the powerful Greek goddess. This pseudonym aptly captured their heroic and assured presence. The participant who had a soft and calm voice as she spoke while giving her words referred as Softy. This participant known as a calm person referred to peace. Another participant that guides ways happened to be called as Fairy. The participant that has a strong feeling was referred to Passion. This participant has a strong sex appeal happened to be called as Sexiness. The angelic voice of this participant called Angel. Next, is the very passionate at its age is Fiery. Lastly, the participant nickname as Buffer who happened to join willingly to help me as a back-up of this research. These nicknames not only added a touch of familiarity but also served as memorable descriptors reflecting the distinct qualities of each participant. The in-depth interviews were done face-to-face at a time that was convenient for each informant. The participants' data was recorded by the researcher using smartphones, which is a crucial step in ensuring the study's validity and reliability.

To ensure a rich understanding of the challenges faced by teachers, participants were meticulously selected. They weren't chosen at random the research criteria focused on educators with experience, valuable insights, and practical recommendations for navigating interactions with overprotective parents. Once identified, each teacher's participation was confirmed through their own personal declaration, solidifying their commitment to the study.

The heart of the research involved in-depth interviews. To prioritize the participants' comfort and convenience, these interviews were conducted face-to-face at their preferred times. Every interview was meticulously recorded using a smartphone, a crucial step in

guaranteeing the study's validity and reliability. This detailed data collection process ensured the capture of every nuance and detail shared by the participating teachers.

The identical set of questions was answered by individual private elementary teachers. According to the criteria we have outlined in them, the participants were chosen by the qualification set. Our contacts with the suggested informants depended on when they had free time. Because of our familiarity with them, we were able to establish the element of trust that was necessary to persuade them to divulge sensitive and enlightening details about the contentious subject. During the interview, some of them were people we had never met before, but they trusted us enough to respond.

The interviews happened through face-to-face interview in depth interview. I used one cell phones for recording along with a notebook to record notes from the interview as suggested by Boyce and Neale (2006). I also asked the informants to sign the informed consent. All of them accommodated the request and had understood but one request that their identity will not be mentioned in the study and will remain confidential from the public.

Categorization of Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding.

Coding is the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

In order to classify the data, the major themes were given in order to address each research question. To give a detailed overview, the study's themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated to provide a vivid description. Then came the conclusion and verification, where the synthesized insights were compared with existing literature to validate the robustness of the findings (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Finally, the culmination of this process offered a comprehensive understanding of the research's implications within the broader scholarly context.

In order to add trustworthiness to the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants have yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information. They all put their signatures on the participant verification form to indicate that they said yes. The triangulation of the study was made possible by the fact that it contained readings from participants and linked works, or more than two sources (Creswell & Miller, 2003).

In order to add trustworthiness to my study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants have yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information and respect their own answers in questions during the interview. They all signed the participant's verification form to confirm their affirmative response. The study's triangulation was made possible by the fact that it included more than two sources, specifically, readings from related literature and participants (Creswell & Miller, 2003).

To ensure dependability and confirmability, the researcher provided an audit trail. This trail was established with the purpose of allowing the research review panel to validate the results, assumptions, and conjectures put forth in the study (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results cannot be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researcher agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Gempes et al., 2009)

Research Question No. 1: What are the lived experiences of elementary teachers in dealing with overprotective parents?

This study explored private elementary teachers' experiences with helicopter parents, focusing on the emotional toll, challenges faced, and coping mechanisms developed. In-depth interviews with fourteen participants revealed three key themes and those are Struggle in Dealing with Various Complaints, Difficulty in Addressing what Overprotective Parents' Want for their Children and Battling to Fulfill the Various Responsibilities as a teacher. The research highlighted the immense pressure teachers face in managing their roles while dealing with overprotective parents. Insights from these narratives aim to inform better communication tools and support systems for teachers.

Struggles in Dealing with Various Complaints

Struggles in dealing with various complaints refer to the challenges faced by individuals, particularly educators, in managing and addressing diverse concerns raised by stakeholders such as parents, students, or colleagues. These complaints can range from academic issues, behavioral concerns, and teaching methods to broader institutional policies. The complexity of these struggles often arises from the need to balance fairness, maintain professionalism, and resolve issues effectively while considering the varying expectations and

emotions of those involved. For teachers, especially, such struggles can become overwhelming when complaints are frequent or perceived as unreasonable, potentially straining their relationships with parents and impacting their focus on fostering a positive learning environment.

Table 2. *Lived Experiences of Elementary Teachers in Dealing with Overprotective Parents*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Struggles in Dealing with Various Complaints	<p>“Of course, I really struggle with parents. I do not know how to stand and handle those parents’ complaints. It is difficult for me to explain to them to make them understand and not get angry because both sides should be listened to. If the child makes a mistake, there shouldn’t be blame because they’re still children, we should just guide them instead of creating conflicts between both parents, not just getting angry immediately.” - IDI-08</p> <p>“I find it difficult with these parents who seem unwilling to discipline their children, even though they know that their child has done something wrong. Perhaps it reflects on the parents because the students’ behaviors often mirror that of their child, although not always, but most of the time, you can say that the child is like that because their parents is also like that.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“In private schools, parents are always considered right here, although their approach may initially seem very understanding, but what they really mean is that you need you gently make them understand. That is because the parents here are our clients since we do not have salaries without them. It is not easy because that is what our principal conversation with them, you need to understand.”- IDI-05</p> <p>“On how I am going to react or what my response will be to the questions from the parents, especially in our group chat. Especially when the parent is somewhat upset, so I find it difficult to respond in a way that would not exacerbate their anger with my reply” - IDI-10</p> <p>“I really struggle with these parents who do not come to school. It is difficult for me to raise my concerns about their child through chat or text because I cannot explain properly to them in person as they might misunderstand, especially since they are overprotective and might overreact.” - IDI-02</p>
Difficulty in Addressing what Overprotective Parents’ Want for their Children	<p>“In my observation, perhaps they spoil their child too much because sometimes they cannot understand the teachers if I have concerns about their child, such as regarding their classmates Because sometimes these kids really argue, especially since they are just in first grade.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“Realistically speaking, you know the parents become overprotective mainly because, in my opinion, here its mostly because their youngest child, the baby, you know, they are very protective of them. So sometimes I cannot blame them because of course the attention is focused on the youngest, especially when they are still in primary grades. They are just in grade three and still very young, that is why they are very caring, especially when it comes to their food and their sensitivity level. They become very emotional and immediately seek comfort from their mom or dad, very dependent. Another thing is, the child is used to being at home with their parents, so when they come to school, they immediately look for their mom and dad. The parents cannot leave right away because the child is very dependent”. - IDI-06</p> <p>“Because parents, you know, always prioritize their children. They do not want their children to get hurt, that is why they are very protective. Maybe it is because they have not experienced or felt pain at home. That is why they become overprotective, especially when their child gets hurt at school, they immediately look for the teacher”. - IDI-08</p> <p>“So, common causes perhaps because most of my students in grade three are academic achievers, so their parents focus a lot on them, especially if they are only children. They immediately react if their scores are low, questioning if the topic was properly taught in class.” - IDI-14</p> <p>“Perhaps the reasons are, firstly, because they are only children, and secondly, because their parents are overly protective even a small injury to their child is often sick, why their parents are overly protective.” - IDI-02</p>
Battling in Fulfilling the Various Responsibilities as a Teacher	<p>“This just happened recently in this school year because there’s this one child who complained to his mother, and it seems like she misunderstood her child’s complaint. Then his mother message me saying “Ma’am, do you know me? I’m so and so’s mother”. And I did not know they were highest member of natives. Then she said “You did not know ma’am, that we can undergo trial, because you told my son about his big teeth’ But she got the wrong Idea about the child complaint, and it was only Through chat because her mom is working abroad. It happened on Saturday, so I haven’t reported it to the principal yet.” – IDI-02</p> <p>One time, a parent complained about the behavior of the student, his son, because his son was overreacting to how I explained to him during those times when he made a mistake. And then his parents is also overprotective, you know. The teacher had not done anything yet, but he was already reacting and creating a problem. So, that is my most unforgettable experience with overprotective parents.” – IDI-07</p> <p>The most unforgettable encounter I had was with this one student whose parents were so overprotective. They complained that their child was being bullied, even though it was not true, it turns out their child was the one bullying his classmates, but he acted like he is the one being bullied. So, his mother came to the school, and I was nervous because she went there and cried, saying I just allowed her child to get hurt. We ended up meeting with the principal at that time.” – IDI-12</p> <p>She complained to me about her child’s grade, comparing it to others. She asked if I favored certain students as a teacher because she didn’t like that her child was ranked lowest.” – IDI-11</p> <p>Those Kids who were fighting, there was one child who started it, but his mother sided his son. She was so overprotective that she sided him, even though her child started it first. Then, another child got involved the principal before she understood the situation.” – IDI-01</p>

The statement of Peace (pseudonym), one of the informants, highlighted the parents' complaints that is definitely one of the toughest parts of their job. They feel lost when faced with their concerns, unsure of how to effectively address them without escalating the situation. Explaining things in a way that fosters understanding and avoids anger on both sides is a constant challenge. It's important to remember that children are still learning and developing, and mistakes are inevitable. Their main focus as a teacher should be on guiding them positively, rather than placing blame. Ideally, open communication between teachers and parents can help us work together to support the child's growth, instead of creating unnecessary conflict. She stated:

“Of course, ma struggle gyud ko sa mga parent I don’t know how to stand and handle those parents complain. Mag lisod kog explain saila nga maliwanagan sila og dili sila masuko kay dapat noth side unta ang paminawon. Kong magkamali man ang bata walay dapat pasad an kay baby paman sila guide nalang nato instead nga mag conflict pa both teacher and parent dili lang pud masuko dayon.” (IDI-08)

(Of course, I really struggle with parents. I do not know how to stand and handle those parents’ complaints. It is difficult for me to explain to them to make them undertsnad and not get angry because both sides should be listened to. If the child makes a mistake, there shouldn’t. be blame because they’re still children we should just guide them instead of creating conflicts between teacher and parents, not just getting angry immediately.)

In addition, the statement of Chatty (pseudonym) shared that teachers often face challenges with parents who appear unwilling to address or discipline their children’s misbehavior, even when they are aware of their child’s faults. This reluctance can be particularly evident in cases of helicopter parenting, where parents may shield their children from consequences instead of fostering accountability. Such behavior can reflect broader parental attitudes, as children’s actions often mirror the values and habits observed at home. She was shared that:

“Mag lisod ko aning mga parents nga murag dili mo sugot disiplinahon ilang anak, bisag kabalo naman sila nga mali ang ge buhat sailang anak. Siguro mo reflect man gud na sa parents kay kong unsa ang estudyante mao pud ang behavior sa ilang anak, although dili gud tanan pero kasagaran gyud mao na maka ingon kag mao diay in ana ang bata kay in ana pud ang ginikanan.” (IDI-04)

(I find it difficult with these parents who seem unwilling to discipline their children, even though they know that their child has done something wrong. Perhaps it reflects on the parents because the students’ behaviors often mirror that of their child, although not always, but most of the time, you can say that the child is like that because their parents is also like that.)

Furthermore, Worry (pseudonym) stated that if the parent’s complaints most especially in private schools, they had no choice but to consider the parents wants. She believed that the parents are their client so they have to follow them also, it was mandated by their principal with regards to this situation. She said:

“In private school man gud always right ang parent diri although okay kaayo at first nila approach piro mao lage well pasabot gyud nimo sila hinay hinay aron makasabot sila. Mao lage ang parent diri is our client kay wala man miy swildo og wala sila. It’s not easy kay mao poy gusto sa among principal nga tarungon nalang gyud silag storya pasabot.” (IDI-05)

(In private schools, parents are always considered right here, although their approach may initially seem very understanding, but what they mean is that you need to gently make them understand. That is because the parents here are our clients since we do not have salaries without them. It is not easy because that is what our principal conversation with them, you need to understand the situation.)

Moreover, Passion (pseudonym) shared her struggles about the different complaints of the parents in their group chats. There are times that the parents are really upset then she cannot reply immediately because she didn’t know how to response and deal with the situation in group chats. She stated that:

“On how I am going to react or unsa on nako pag response nako sa mga questions sa mga parents especially sa among group chat. Labi nag medyo nag lagot ang parent so maglisod kog response nga kana ganing di pud maka samot saiyang kalagot akong reply.” (IDI-10)

(On how I am going to react or what my response will be to the questions from the parents, especially in our group chat. Also especially when the parents is somewhat upset, so I find it difficult to respond in a way that would not exacerbate their anger with my reply.)

According to Mushroom (pseudonym), she said that it was incredibly frustrating dealing with uninvolved parents who skip meetings. Text or chat makes it hard to explain concerns effectively, especially with overprotective parents who might misinterpret any criticism and potentially overreact due to their protectiveness. This lack of face-to-face interaction makes building rapport difficult, hindering open communication crucial for addressing the student's needs. Her statement was:

“Mag lisod gyud ko aning mga parent nga dili mo adto sa eskwelahan. Hmm mag lisod ko og raise sa akong concern about sailang anak through chat or text kay dili nako ma explain og tarong saila sa personal kay basig malain nilag sabot labi na kay overprotective basig mag over reacting pud.” (IDI-02)

(I really struggle with these parents who do not come to school. It is difficult for me to raise my concerns about their child through chat or text because I cannot explain properly to them in person as they might misunderstand, especially since they are overprotective and might overreact.”)

Difficulty in Addressing what Overprotective Parents wants to their Children

Difficulty in addressing what overprotective parents want for their children involves the challenges of managing the high expectations and demands placed by parents who are deeply involved in every aspect of their child's life. Overprotective parents often advocate for their children in ways that may conflict with professional judgments, creating obstacles in balancing parental preferences with what is deemed appropriate or beneficial. This difficulty includes handling constant interventions, unreasonable requests, or conflicting opinions, which can complicate decision-making and create tension in communication.

Talking to overprotective parents about letting go can be a tightrope walk. They often come from a place of love and fear, making it hard to explain that their constant hovering hinders a child's ability to develop independence, problem-solving skills, and resilience. One of the statement of Congenial (pseudonym) stated that some parents are letting their kids on how they behave in school and it makes harder for them to deal with bad behavior of the student at school. This could be because they struggle to see their child's role in classmate arguments, especially considering it's a common occurrence in first grade. Her statement was:

“Sa akong Nakita og na observe saila siguro na subraan ra pud sirugo nila ka pinangga or na spoiled kay nakita nako usahay di na sila makasabot sa teacher if naa koy concern sailang anak like with regards to their classmates kay usahay mag away-away gyud ning mga bata labi na kay grade one pa.” (IDI-03)

(In my observation, perhaps they spoil their child too much because sometimes they cannot understand the teachers if I have concerns about their child, such as regarding their classmates Because sometimes these kids really argue, especially since they are just in first grade.)

According to Hera (pseudonym) the youngest child's situation fosters overprotectiveness. Parents naturally prioritize their youngest, and the child's comfort needs (like specific food) and clingy behavior at school create a dynamic where addressing those needs becomes a cycle that reinforces the overprotectiveness, making it harder for the teacher to fully support the child. She stated:

“Realistically speaking ha' kaya nagiging overprotective ang parent kasi para sa akin lang ha' mostly kasi dito kay bunsong anak, kinamanghoran. So usahay dili nako sila masisi kay sympre kinamanghoran ang attention naa saila naka focus labi nag kay naa pa sa primary grade. Grade three pa tapos bata pa kaayo maong caring kaayo sila when it comes to their food especially the level of their sensitivity very emotional tug an dayon sa mama/papa very dependent. Another thing is ang bata is nasanay siya sa bahay together with their parent so inig abot sa school hanapin talaga agad yung mama/papa hindi agad makaalis ang parent kasi very dependent ang bata.” (IDI-06)

(Realistically speaking, you know the parents become overprotective mainly because, in my opinion, here its mostly because their youngest child, the baby, you know, they are very protective of them. So, sometimes I cannot blame them because of course the attention is focused on the youngest, especially when they are primary grades. They are just in grade three and still very young, that is why they are very caring, especially when it comes to their food and their sensitivity level. They become very emotional and immediately seek comfort from their mom or dad, very dependent. Another thing is, the child is used to being at home with their parents, so when they come to school, they immediately look for their mom and dad. The parents cannot leave right away because the child is very dependent”.)

In addition, the statement of Peace (pseudonym) that there is a misconception sometimes. While parents naturally want to shield their children from harm, overprotectiveness might stem from a lack of their own childhood experiences with navigating challenges. This can lead to a quick reaction of blaming teachers when their child gets hurt at school, and sometimes the teacher didn't know what to do. She stated that:

“Basta parent man gud number one dika gusto masakitan imong anak mao sirugo di gyud nila gusto masakitan ilang anak siguro pud kay saila wala na nila nadapatan or wala nakabatig kasakit sa balay. Maong mag overprotective sila pag masakitan na sa school syempre ang teacher dayon na ilang pangitaon.” (IDI-08)

(Because parents, you know, always prioritize their children. They do not want their child to get hurt, that is why they are very protective. Myabe it is because they have not experienced or felt pain at home. That is why they become overprotective, especially when their child gets hurt at school, they immediately look for the teacher.)

Moreover, the statement of Buffer (pseudonym) said that his third graders had a high achievement and only-child status might explain their parents' close involvement. Since these students excel academically, their parents likely prioritize education and may be more sensitive to lower scores. This can lead to them questioning the teaching methods if their child's performance got low average. As he shared that:

“So, common causes Seguro kay most of my student man gud in grade three is academic achiever so focus ilang parents saila labi na kay only child. Mo react dayon nganong gamay ang score nag klase ba gyud daw tarong ana nga topic.” (IDI-14)

(So, common causes perhaps because most of my students in grade three are academic achievers, so their parents focus a lot on them, especially if they are only children. They immediately react if their scores are low, questioning if the topic was properly taught in class.”)

Furthermore, the statement of Mushroom (pseudonym) showed two things might explain why some parents seem overly protective. First, if their child is an only child, they might receive all their attention and care, making them focus more on any bumps or bruises. Second, these parents themselves might be extra cautious, considering even minor injuries a sign of serious illness. As Mushroom (pseudonym) explains that:

“Reasons siguro una is kanang only child lang tapos kanang overprotective kayo sila like gamay lang nga nasakitan ilang anak mabalaka na sila. Siguro pud kay masakiton pud ang bata maong overprotective kayo sila.” (IDI-02)

(Perhaps the reasons are, firstly, because they are only children, and secondly, because their parents are overly protective even a small injury to their child is often sick, which is why their parents are overly protective.)

Battling Fulfilling the Various Responsibilities as a Teachers

Battling fulfilling the various responsibilities as a teacher involves struggling to manage the wide range of tasks and expectations that come with the role. These responsibilities include delivering effective lessons, assessing student progress, maintaining discipline, fostering relationships with students and parents, and participating in school activities and administrative tasks. Balancing these duties can be challenging, especially when resources, time, or support are limited, often leading to stress and burnout.

Teaching is a beautiful dance between competing priorities. You strive to deliver engaging lessons, nurture individual growth, and navigate ever-changing demands. Just like the statement of Mushroom (pseudonym), highlighted her situation in a communication misunderstanding she had experience. A student recently complained to his mom, who works abroad and communicates through chat. Unfortunately, the mom misinterpreted the complaint and mistakenly thought you threatened her son with legal action ("trial") for having big teeth. It seems you were simply discussing the child's dental health in a casual way. She shared:

“Kani bag o lang ni nahitabo karon lang nga school year kay naa tuy ika-isa nga kaning ni sumbong siya tapos murag na misinterpret niya ang sumbog saiyang anak. Unya nag chat iyang mama sa akoo. ‘maam kaila kas akoo maam?, ako biya si kuan maam’ unya karon wala ko kabalo nga kini diay sila kay member og mga native gud tapos ana siya ‘wala ka kabalo maam nga pwede ka namo mapatanggal tapos ipa tribal ka namo sa imong ge sulti sa among anak kay ge ingnan nimo siyag dakog ngipon’. Piro namali gyud tug sumbong sa bata tapos through chat raman gud ge sumbong sa bata kay tuag abroad ang iyang mama. Saturday pa gyud ato so wala dayon nako na sumbong sa principal” (IDI-02)

(This just happened recently in this school year because there's this one child who complained to his mother, and it seems like she misunderstood her child's complaint. Then his mother message me saying ‘Ma'am, do you know me? I'm so and so's mother'. And I didn't know they were highest member of natives. Then she said ‘You did not know ma'am, that we can undergo trial through tribal, because you told my son about his big teeth’. But she got the wrong Idea about the child's complaint, and it was only through chat because her mom is working abroad. It happened on Saturday, so I haven't reported it to the principal yet that time.”

In addition, the statement of Softy (pseudonym) said that she had experience with overprotective parents it is because of the student's behavior. The parent complained that their son, likely due to their protectiveness, would overreact before I even had a chance to address his mistake and this created unnecessary tension. It highlighted the challenge of navigating overprotective tendencies, where parents' good intentions can unintentionally hinder their child's ability to learn from constructive feedback. She stated that:

“One time that a parent complain somehow the behavior of the student about his son. His son is being over reacting on how I explain to him those times nga maka sala siya and then iyang parents is also overprotective do, wala pang ginagawa si teacher but he is already reacting and created a problem so, that is my most unforgettable experience with overprotective parents.” (IDI-07)

(One time, a parent complained about the behavior of the student, his son, because his son was overreacting to how I explained to him during those times when he made a mistakes. And then his parents is also overprotective, you know. The teacher had not done anything yet, but he was already reacting and creating a problem. So, that is my most unforgettable experience with overprotective parents.)

Furthermore, Angel (pseudonym) shared her experience about her battle against the parents that believed their child was being bullied, and the mother came to school very upset, even crying, accusing her of neglecting their son's safety. However, after investigation, it turned out the student was actually the bully, cleverly manipulating the situation to appear like the victim. This unexpected twist led to a meeting with the principal. She stated:

“Ang most unforgettable gyud nga akong na encounter kay tung naay overprotective parent ng ani adto diria kay nag reklamo siya saiyang anak ban ga gina-bully. Mao to ni adto iyang mama unya nakulbaan ko kay ni adto gyud sa school unya nag hilak-hilak kay gina-pasagdan daw nako masakitan iyang anak naabot pud mig principal ato.” (IDI-12)

(The most unforgettable encounter I had with this one student whose parents were so overprotective. They complained that their child was being bullied, even though it was not true, it turns out their child was the one bullying his classmate, but he acted like he is the one being bullied. So, his mother came to the school, and I was nervous because she went there and cried, saying I just allowed her child to get hurt. We ended up meeting with the principal at that time.

In addition, the statement of Kind (pseudonym) described a frustrating situation involving a physical altercation between students.

Despite clear evidence that one child initiated the fight, the overprotective mother immediately came to her son's defense, refusing to acknowledge any wrongdoing. This scenario highlights a key difficulty teachers face: parents who, through their protectiveness, unintentionally obstruct the conflict resolution process. By refusing to accept their child's responsibility, such parents can erode the teacher's authority and make it challenging to establish a fair and consistent disciplinary approach for the entire class. She stated:

“Ahh.. Kadtong mga bata nga nag away, naay bata nagaway piro ge labanan pa siya sa iyang mama and overprotective kaayo siya labanan gyud niya bisag iyang anak nag una-una tapos mali sa iynag anak. Na involved pa isang ka bata sa principal bago pa siya nakasabot.” (IDI-01)

(Those kids who were fighting, there was one child who started it, but his mother sided his son. She was so overprotective that she sided him, even though her child started it first. Then, another child got involved the principal before she understood the situation.)

Research Question No. 2: How do elementary teachers cope with the challenges in helicopter parenting?

The second major question is elementary school teachers' actual interactions with overly protective parents. It aims to comprehend the difficulties they encounter, the kinds of scenarios that emerge, and the emotional resonance of these exchanges. Through compiling these firsthand accounts, scholars or instructors can acquire important knowledge. These could include establishing precise boundaries for communication with parents, concentrating on factual reports of student conduct, and seek for help with others stakeholders and staff. Teachers may foster a more harmonious and productive environment for both themselves and their pupils by implementing these tactics. There are three emerging themes that the researcher had found after thorough analysis considering all the participants' responses. These themes were: Employing effective personal strategies to deal with helicopter parents, implementing the school and classroom rule and regulations and conducting parents orientation every first day of the school year. Below was the presentation of the emerging themes together with the supporting statements provided by the participants.

Table 3. Coping Mechanisms of Elementary Teachers with the Challenges Faced in Dealing with Helicopter Parents

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Employing Effective Personal Strategies to Deal with Helicopter Parents	<p>“You should listen to his side and also explain your side to him, not just make it seem like you are overpowering him. Respect should still be maintained, with ‘po and ‘opo’ and a polite ‘good morning’. Even if you’re already angry, you should still treat them with kindness, let’s just always lower ourselves.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“First thing first is you need to talk with the parents. We should not discuss things inside the classroom where the children can see us; we should talk outside. Then, calmly talk to the parents. If you cannot handle it, we need to go to the guidance office and ask for assistance. The teacher should be present, of course and if it still cannot be resolved, that is the time that a principal should get involved” IDI-06</p> <p>“My strategy is first and foremost, stay calm. Remain calm no matter how frustrated; you need to calm yourself down because you are dealing with a parent. And if they start to get angry, I would not escalate the situation by matching their anger, I will stay calm, because that is how a teacher should handle the parents.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“My strategy is to keep them updated on their child’s standing in school so they do not overthink or wonder why their child’s grades are the way they are at the end of the day. This way, they would not have anything to blame me for.” - IDI-12</p> <p>“You will talk to them one on one; you will let them stay in the classroom, and then you will talk to them first, and if someone else shouts at you, you will just listen to them after they calm down, and then you will slowly explain the situation to the child. You will have a problem with these children because they are very stubborn and aggressive, you will be the one to answer to their parents about their behavior.” - IDI-05</p>
Implementing the School and Classroom Rules and Regulations	<p>“I will just explain to the parents that as a teacher, I have my own rules and I strictly adhere to what has been set regarding the rules. My rules are also for their child’s benefit, ensuring that no one gets hurt and that there’s no need for any reaction. I communicate this to foster understanding. It is also very unfair if their child is exempted, so everyone should abide by the school rules.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“Before they enrolled here, before they sent their child to school here, there was an orientation for parents at the school so they could understand up to what extent they need to comply with the rules here. As a grade one adviser, I just remind the parents of the school rules.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“How do I manage? I manage discipline through the rules I established, such as no cellphone during classes. Beforehand they should only call during recess, lunch break, and after dismissal. Now that children have gadgets, this discipline proven to be very effective, especially with the collaboration of parents as well.” - IDI-09</p> <p>“There is no other way but to clearly explain my rules in terms of discipline so that the parents know if their child has done something wrong, they would not tolerate it but instead assist the teacher in disciplining the child.” - IDI-08</p> <p>“I explain to them that outside of the classroom, ma’am or sir, it is you who make the rules for your child. So, when they’re at school, especially under my care, I want my rules to be supported by them to ensure that their child listens to me because its ultimately for their child’s benefit.” - IDI-02</p>
Conducting Parent Orientation Every First Day of the School Year	<p>“Before they enrolled here, before they sent their child to school here, there was an orientation for parents at the school so they could understand up to what extent they could understand up to what extent they need to comply with the rules here. As a grade one Adviser, I just remind the parents of the school rules.” – IDI-03</p> <p>“Disciplining is not easy, especially since there are many of them, but my approach is to seek help form the parents so I can have support in correcting their children’s behavior. That is why I coordinate with the parents</p>

through parent orientation, so they are also aware of the rules for their children and can enforce them at home. When they come to school, I just give a gentle reminder because we really cannot act as disciplinarians as a teacher.” – IDI-14

“Right from the beginning of the school year, we have a parent orientation where each parent is briefed on the school rules, ensuring that everyone understands them clearly.” – IDI-11

“On the very first day of the school year, I make sure to enforce the classroom rules through parent orientation so that there are no questions from the parents. The parents are also made aware of the school rules, including the classroom rules like fines. I also inform the children and their parents about this through our group chats.” – IDI-10

“I make it clear to them beforehand that once their child is brought to school here, especially if they are in grade two, they automatically fall under my rules. But once they are outside, it is up to the parents again. They were already oriented during the parent conferences, so they know that my rules apply when their child is at school.

Explaining this to the parents is really challenging, especially because their behavior is also diverse.” – IDI-05

Employing Effective Personal Strategies to Deal with Helicopter Parents

Employing effective personal involves using targeted approaches to manage the challenges posed by over-involved parents. These strategies may include setting clear boundaries, maintaining open and respectful communication, and educating parents on the benefits of fostering independence in their children. Teachers might also use proactive problem-solving techniques, offer regular updates on student progress, and create opportunities for constructive collaboration. Moreover, through developing these strategies, educators can maintain a positive working relationship with parents while ensuring the child's autonomy and educational growth are not compromised.

According to Chatty (pseudonym), recognizing the importance of active listening in navigating interactions with overprotective parents resonated strongly with one participant, Chatty (pseudonym). Through actively listening to their concerns and anxieties, teachers can build rapport and open the door for more productive communication. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of the parent's motivations and paves the way for developing solutions that benefit both the child and the classroom environment as a whole. She stated:

“Sabton nimo iyang side og pasabton pud nimo siya saimong side dili lang murag labwan nimo siya. Respect gihapon ka mag “po” at “opo” ana gyud tapos mag “good morning”. Bahala gud suko na gud ka piro abi-abihon gihapon nimo sila, paubos lang gyud ta kanunay.” (IDI-04)

(You should listen to their side and also explain your side to him, not just make it seem like you are overpowering him. Respect should still be maintained, with “po and “opo” and a polite “good morning”. Even if you're already angry, you should still treat them with kindness, lets just always lower ourselves.)

Also, the statement of Hera (pseudonym) said that the teacher should provide a step-by-step approach or process in dealing with parent concerns. It emphasizes the importance of clear communication and escalating the issue if necessary. She stated that:

“First things first is you need to talk with the parents, we don't need to talk inside of the classroom nga makita sa mga bata we should talk outside. Then talk to the parents calmly if hindi mo kaya we need to go at the guidance office ask for assistance and then the teacher should be present of course kong dili gihapon makaya that's the time nga ma involve na ang pricipal.” (IDI-06)

(First thing first is you need to talk with the parents. We should not discuss things inside the classroom where the children can see us; we should talk outside. Then calmly talk to the parents. If you cannot handle it, we need to go to the guidance office and ask for assistance. The teacher should be present, of course and if it still cannot be resolved, that's the time that a principal should get involved.)

In addition, the statement of Kind (pseudonym) highlights a strategy by prioritize of being calm, even how frustrated she is. She also emphasizes about being a role model, so escalating with anger would not help. Instead, she maintains composure to de-escalate the situation and work towards a solution with the parent.

“Akong strategy is at first is calm lang gyud kalma lang. Kalma lang gyud ka maskin nag suko na kaayo ka kinahanglan ikalma gyud nimo imong sarili kay sympre kay parent man gud imong kaatubang. Og mo abot na siya sa point nga suko na gyud kaayo siya dili pud nako siya level'an saiyang kasuko tapos kalma ra gyud dapat ka, kay dapat in ana gyud ang teacher inig atubang sa parents.” (IDI-01)

(My strategy is first and foremost, to stay calm. Remain calm no matter how frustrated you may feel; you need to calm yourself down because you are dealing with a parent. And if they start to get angry, I would not escalate the situation by matching their anger, I will stay calm, because that is how a teacher should handle the parents.)

Furthermore, the statement of Angel (pseudonym) highlighted a strategy through proactive communication. By keeping parents regularly updated on their child's progress in class, good or bad, I can prevent misunderstandings. This transparency avoids situations where parents might overthink or suspect something negative about their child's grades. Open communication fosters trust and reduces the chance of blame being placed on me later. She stated:

“Kuan akong strategy gyud kay gina-update naki sila sa standing sa ilang anak sa school aron dili na sila mag overthink og matingala

at the end of the day ngano in ana ra ang grado sailang anak. Aron pud wala silay ikasumbat sa akoo.” (IDI-12)

(My strategy is to keep them updated on their child’s standing in school so that they don’t have to overthink or wonder why their child’s grades are the way they are at the end of the day. In this way, they would not have anything to blame me for.)

Another statement from Worry (pseudonym) primary emphasizes on how to address issues one-on-one. Like, first talk privately in the classroom. There are cases that sometimes the children are aggressive and if something will happen the teacher is the one how’s responsible for it. She stated:

“Imo siyang storyahon one on one, imo siyang padayunon sa classroom tapos una ana imo sa gyud siyang pa isturyahon, unya naa gane uban mangasaba na dayon imoha nalang gyud mapinawon after niya makalma tapos diha pako mag hinay-hinay og explain sa sitwasyon sa iyang anak. Mag problema ka aning mga bata man gud kiat kaayo unyag mangatusok og mangasamad nana’ ikaw gyud ang manubag sa ilang mga ginikanan” (IDI-05)

(You will talk to them one on one; you will let them stay in the classroom, and then you will talk to them first, and if someone else shouts at you, you will just listen to them especially the parents. After they calm down, and then you will slowly explain the situation with regards to their child. You will be the one to answer to their parents about their behavior)

Implementing the School and Classroom Rules and Regulations

Establishing, enforcing, and maintaining a set of guidelines that govern student behavior and foster a productive learning environment is a critical aspect of effective classroom management. This process involves clearly articulating expectations, consistently applying rules, and addressing violations with fairness and structure. It also necessitates cultivating an atmosphere of mutual respect, accountability, and trust, where students not only understand the consequences of their actions but also grasp the significance of adhering to established norms. By maintaining consistency and transparency, teachers create a safe and supportive space that minimizes disruptions, allowing both teaching and learning to flourish. Effective implementation of these guidelines promotes positive behavior, encourages student growth, and ensures a harmonious classroom dynamic.

The participant highlights the importance of clear and consistent school and classroom rules benefit everyone involved in the learning process. Teachers can create a well-managed environment that fosters learning. Parents can feel confident their children are in a safe and predictable space. Most importantly, students benefit from a structured learning environment that allows them to focus on academic and social development. When everyone understands the expectations, it reduces confusion, minimizes disruptions, and ultimately creates a more positive and productive learning experience for all. Like Chatty (pseudonym), one of the informants, highlighted the importance of setting fair school rules that will benefit her students. She stated like this:

“Ipasabot lang gyud nako sa mga ginikanan nga ako as a teacher naa koy akong rules and ga follow ra pud ko kong unsa ingon sa amoa about sa rules. Kana akong rules kay para raman pud na sailang anak og di man lang makasakit sa bata wala nay dapat i-react, kana akong gina ingon aron magkasabot. Unfair man pud kaayo og exemted iyang anak so dapat tanan gyud sila under sa school rules.” (IDI-04)

(I will just explain to the parents that as a teacher, I have my own rules and I strictly adhere to what has been set regarding the rules. My rules are also for their child’s benefit, ensuring that no one gets hurt and by that there’s no need for any reaction. I communicate this with them to foster better understanding. It is also very unfair if their child is exempted, so everyone should abide by the school rules.)

In addition, Congenial (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of holding a parent orientation before enrollment, ensuring that all parties are aligned from the very beginning. These orientation meetings serve to clearly communicate the school’s expectations for both students and parents, laying the groundwork for a collaborative and successful academic year. By setting clear guidelines and fostering open communication, these sessions help establish mutual understanding and commitment, which can contribute to a positive and supportive school environment throughout the year. As the participant uttered that:

“Before sila nag enroll diri, before nila gipa eskwela ilang anak diri kay naa gyud orientation sa mga parents sa school so makasabot sila hantod asa lang sila taman diri pariha sa rules. Ako as a grade one adviser gina-remind nalang nako ang mga parent sa school rules.” (IDI-03)

(Before they enrolled here, before they sent their child to school here, there was an orientation for parents at the school so they could understand up to what extent they need to comply with the rules here. As a grade one adviser, I just remind the parents of the school rules.”

According to Fairy (pseudonym), her approach to classroom discipline relies heavily on establishing clear and straightforward rules, such as no phones during class time. She communicates this expectation to students from the outset, ensuring they understand that phone use is only permitted during breaks and after dismissal. Furthermore, she makes sure that parents are also informed about this rule, fostering consistency between home and school. She expresses:

“I manage my discipline through sa rules nga akong ge buhat like no cellphones during classes. Before pa maka-react ang mga ginikanan

labi natong mga overprotective kaayo seg tawag og text sailang anak, ge ingnan na nako sila daan nga manawag lang during recess, lunch break and ting uliian na. Karon man gud naa nay mga gadget ang mga bata so kani palang nga classroom rule effective kaayo with the collaboration of their parents as well.” (IDI-09)

(I manage discipline through the rules I have establish, such as no cellphone during classes. Beforehand that they should only call during recess, lunch break and after dismissal. Now that children have gadgets, this classroom discipline has proven to be very effective, especially with the collaboration of their parents as well.)

Also, the statement of Peace (pseudonym) said that she clearly explains her classroom rules for both students and parents. This transparency means parents understand her expectations and won't be surprised if their child breaks a rule. Ideally, this fosters collaboration where parents support the consequences if their child will not follow to the rules that is being implemented, creating a consistent approach to discipline that benefits the child's behavior. She stated like this:

“No other way but to explain my rules in terms of discipline kay para alam ni parent if naay mali ang bata they won't tolerate instead tabangan ang teacher aron ma disiplina ang bata.” (IDI-08)

(There is no other way butt to clearly explain my rules in terms of discipline so that the parents know of their child had done something wrong, they would not tolerate it but instead assist the teacher in disciplining the child.)

Moreover, the statement of Mushroom (pseudonym) tells that in her classroom, she strives for clear communication with parents. She explains that while they set the rules at home, when their child is under her care at school, her rules take precedence. Most importantly, she emphasizes that following classroom rules is ultimately beneficial for their child's learning and development. By seeking their support, I create a unified approach that benefits everyone. She stated:

“Gina-pasabot nako sila nga outside of the classroom ma'am/sir, kamo ang ga buhat og rules para sa inyong anak so, if naan a sila sa school labi na kay under sa akoa gusto nako sa akoa pud rules tanganan ko nila aron maminaw ilang anak sa akoa kay parra raman gihapon ni sailang anak tanan.” (IDI-02)

(I explain to them that outside of the classroom, ma'am or sir, it is you who makes the rules for your child. So, when they're at school, especially under my care, I want my rules to be supported by them to ensure that their child will listens to me because its ultimately for their child's benefit.)

Conducting Parents Orientation Every First day of the School Year

Conducting parents' orientation every first day of the school year refers to the practice of organizing a meeting or event at the beginning of each academic year to introduce parents to the school's policies, expectations, and key programs. This orientation serves as an opportunity to build strong communication between parents and teachers, ensuring that everyone is aligned on educational goals, classroom rules, and the support needed for student success. It also allows parents to ask questions, meet staff members, and better understand how they can contribute to their child's learning and development throughout the year.

Schools hold parent orientation once at the year's beginning, not every first day. This initial orientation serves a crucial purpose; it establishes clear communication channels, outlines school rules and expectations, and allows parents to meet the teachers. This early introduction fosters a strong foundation for a successful year for students, parents, and teachers alike. So, the parent's orientation should be done at the very first day of the school year. Just like what Buffer (pseudonym) said about the advantage of setting or having a parent orientation that will help him to coordinate with the parents in terms of disciplining their child. He uttered:

“Dili man gyud lalim ang pag disiplina labi na kay daghan sila no' piro akong paagi lang gyud kay mangayo kog tabang sa parents aron naa koy kalalay sa pag badlong sailang mga anak. Mao ra gyud na akoa makig coordinate sa mga ginikanan through parent orientation, para aware sila sa Batasan sa ilang anak og mabadlong pud nila sa ilang balay aron inig abot sa eskwelahan kasaba nalang ginagmay akoa, kay di biya gyud pwede mangdapat ta as a teacher.” (IDI-14)

(Disciplining is not easy, especially since there are many of them, but my approach is to seek help form the parents so I can have support in correcting their children's behavior. That is why I coordinate with the parents through parent orientation, so they are also aware of the rules for their children and can enforce them at home. When they come to school, I just give a gentle reminder because we really cannot hurt them as a teacher)”

According to Sexiness (pseudonym), she said that their school prioritizes a parent orientation at the beginning of the year. To ensures all parents are clearly briefed on the school rules. By establishing a shared understanding from the outset, we can work together to create a positive and productive learning environment for all students. Her statement was:

“Sa sugod palang daan sa school year naa gyud miy parents orientation og na isa-isa na gyud nag pahibalo ang mga rules sa parent unya og gina-explain gyud saila aron magkasinabot pud.” (IDI-11)

(Right from the beginning of the school year, we have a parent orientation where each parents is briefed on the school rules, ensuring that everyone understands them clearly.)

Furthermore, the statement of Passion (pseudonym) tells that to ensure a smooth start to the year, she enforce classroom rules right from the beginning. During the first-day parent orientation. This information is also shared through class group chat, making sure both parents and students are aware of expectation. She stated:

“At the first day palang gyud sa school year ge impose gyud na nako akong classroom rules through parents orientation para walay questions ang mga parents. Also aware naman ang mga parents sa school rules kana sa classroom rules like fines, gina ingnan pud nako mga bata ana and their parent through our GC’s.” (IDI-10)

(On the very first day of the school year, I make sure to enforce the classroom rules through parents orientation so that there are no questions from the parents. The parents are also made aware of the school rules, including the classroom rules like fines. I also inform the children and their parents about this through our group chats.)

In addition, Worry (pseudonym) said the about It's crucial to establish boundaries she told the parents that although they establish the ground rules at home, her rules are essential when their child is in the classroom. Although parents handle things differently, so it can be difficult, she wants to stress that these expectations were already presented in the parent orientation. This openness encourages teamwork and keeps everyone in agreement, which eventually helps the child's learning. She stated:

“Ako gyud na silang ginapasabot daan nga diri sa eskwelahan pag mahatod gane na diri kay gina hatod-hatod paman gyud na kay grade two paman. Automatic under nana sila sa akong rules piro inig gawas na ana nila ang parent na ang bahala nasad. Tapos na orient na gyud na sila daan tong time sa parent conferencing so, kabalo nana sila nga ako na gyud na rules pag naan a ilang anak sa eskwelaha. Ang pagsabot ra gyud sa ginikanan mao gyud na lisod labi na kay diverse pud ilang behavior.” (IDI-05)

(I make it clear to them that once their child is brought to school here, especially if they are in grade two, they automatically fall under my rules But once they are outside, it is up to the parents again. They were already oriented during the parent conferences, so they know that my rules apply when their child is at school. Explaining this to the parents is really challenging, especially because they are also diverse.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the elementary teacher’s recommendations in dealing the overprotective parents?

Elementary teachers participating in the study emphasized the importance of recognizing that overprotective parents often act out of genuine concern for their child’s well-being. However, their protectiveness can sometimes hinder a child's development. To bridge this gap, teachers recommend establishing clear communication about classroom expectations and providing regular progress updates. This not only sets boundaries but also allows teachers to work collaboratively with parents. The goal is to foster a shared understanding of how best to support the child's growth, independence, and resilience. This process involved a deep dive into each teacher's perspective, uncovering the underlying themes that resonated throughout their narratives. Through this analysis, three key themes emerged are The Value of Strengthening Collaboration and Patience between Teachers and Parents, The Importance of Communication Between Parents, Teachers, and Department of Education and last theme is Foster Good Association Between School and its Stakeholders.

Table 4. Insights of Elementary Teachers in with Overprotective Parents

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
The Value of Strengthening Collaboration and Patience Between Teachers and Parents	<p>“Just stay calm, and make sure both the child and the mother stay calm as well. If you get angry at the child, you need to have patience with both the child and the mother. Because if you get angry at just one child, you might end up scolding everyone in general, not just the one child. So, it is not like ‘Oh, the teacher scolded me at school’, and then the mother will scold them, and that is when problems arise.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“As for that, I think it is about collaboration. We need to collaborate with the parents because they are part of the school organization, and it is also about the school’s partnership. All we need to do as a teacher is to build a strong relationship with the parents because without that, we would not understand each other. Because the good start is building a strong relationship.” - IDI-06</p> <p>“For other teachers, dealing with overprotective parents is really challenging, but we have to adjust and be patient. The teachers’ actions should be correct so that parents have no complaints. As teachers, were not perfect, and if we make mistakes, especially if we say something to their child, we should apologize immediately to avoid escalating the problem and ask for their forgiveness, that’s all.” - IDI-11</p> <p>“The lesson here is that we really need to give them attention. We should consistently update them regarding their child’s performance, and if they have questions, we should respond in a proper manner. We should not do anything that might trigger their anger about their child; the teacher should always remain calm. If as a teacher, you have a complaint about a child, ask their parents about it in the right way to avoid any trouble, and so they would not have negative comments about you either.” - IDI-09</p>
The Importance of Communication Between Parents, Teachers and Department of Education	<p>My suggestion is that parents should investigate the situation first. For example, if their child tells them something, and then they complain, the teacher should respond promptly. I saw on Facebook that the teacher got angry because the child could not read ang poked him with a pen, causing bleeding. The parent even went to the police and posted on social media that there is a teacher who yells without patience and that is why the child misbehaved. Especially with the Department of Education, because there are many children being handled, you should be very careful with your actions and words because we are afraid of losing our jobs because of such students and parents.” - IDI-02</p> <p>Perhaps in DepEd, there should be a parent orientation to explain to parents their role in their children’s</p>

schooling once they're inside the school. Both parents and teachers need to collaborate to facilitate the child's learning, so their cooperation is essential. Again, parents should be well oriented to avoid any issues." - IDI-03
 For the suggestions and recommendations in DepEd, I believe that public school teachers handle a large number of students, and we all know that learners are diverse and unique, with different needs. Because of this, teachers especially those in public schools, often encounter struggles and problems in handling their students. Therefore, they should reduce the number of students in each classroom. For example, if a classroom is supposed to accommodate a certain number of students, and as a teacher, you find it difficult you manage all of them. Probably, reducing the number of students would be beneficial. That is my overall suggestion to DepEd." - IDI-06

My advice to DepEd is for them to conduct seminars for teachers and parents. Through this, parents and teacher will know their boundaries when it comes to dealing with children, and everyone will be oriented to avoid situations where misunderstandings may arise." - IDI-08

"My suggestion to schools and to DepEd is that if there are overprotective parents, they should conduct orientations for parents and create programs to educate them about what should and should not happen within the school." IDI-12

Foster Good Association
 Between School and Its
 Stakeholders

Instead of considering them as adversaries, you should regard them as your friends. Maintain a friendly attitude at all times, and I believe that any past misunderstanding. Just let go and forgive because you love your job, and both children and parents are part of your Profession." - IDI-06

To establish good relationship, there should be love and respect, along with good communication with the parents. Also, learn to love their child as if they were your own because when parents see that we genuinely care for their child, that's when their trust in us begins." - IDI-09

Make them your friends, be friend them, communicate with them, talk to them casually yet respectfully most of the time. Then, provide for the needs of their children because that's really what they want for their children to receive attention in school." - IDI-13

As I always do, I remain calm all the times and learn to accept that there are indeed parents like that. It is normal, and it is your job as a teacher to deal with it. Also, if you meet them, address them and respond respectfully and with a smile, so they feel comfortable with you." - IDI-10

Always address the parents with respect because they are also part of the school as a stakeholder. If you need to, smile every time you see them at school in order for the parents to appreciate you." - IDI-11

The Value of Strengthening Collaboration and Patience Between Teacher and Parent

The value of strengthening collaboration and patience between teachers and parents lies in fostering a supportive and effective learning environment for the child. When teachers and parents work together, sharing insights, concerns, and strategies, it creates a unified approach to addressing the child's academic, social, and emotional needs. Patience is crucial in this partnership, as both parties may have differing perspectives, but by maintaining open communication and mutual respect, they can navigate challenges more effectively. A strong collaboration between teachers and parents helps ensure consistent support for the child, enhances their development, and promotes a positive educational experience.

The statement of Kind (pseudonym) shared about maintaining a calm demeanor in the face of frustration is paramount when dealing with overprotective parents. Reacting with anger towards either the child or the parent is counterproductive. Escalating emotions can shut down communication and prevent a productive resolution. Patience is key for both the child and the parent. By taking a deep breath and approaching the situation calmly, teachers can create a safe space for open dialogue. This allows everyone involved to voice their concerns and work collaboratively towards a solution. Avoiding a cycle of reprimands and negativity keeps the focus on positive reinforcement and fostering a collaborative approach to supporting the child's development. In this calm environment, everyone can contribute constructively, leading to a more positive outcome for all parties involved. She stated:

"Kalma lang gihapon ka unya kuan lang kaning kalmado sila sa bata og kalmado lang oud sila sa mama. Kong masuko ka sa mga bata og mapagpasensya pud ka sa mama kay kong masuko gyud ka sa isa lang ka bata i-general nalang ang kasaba dili lang sa isa ka bata sila nalang tanan. Para dili "hala ge kasab an diay kong teacher" sa school unya tug-an dayon sa iyang mama diba, unya diha na gyud na magkaproblema." (IDI-01)

(Just stay calm, and make sure both the child and the mother stay calm as well. If you get angry at the child, you need to have patience with both child and the mother. Because if you get angry at just one child, you might end up scolding everyone in general way, not just the one child. So, it is not like "oh, the teacher scolded me at school", and then the mother will also scold you, and that is when problems arise.)

Furthermore, the statement of Hera (pseudonym) tells that effective classroom management hinges on collaboration with parents. They're partners in a child's education, and a strong teacher-parent relationship is crucial. By fostering open communication and building trust, you create a foundation for mutual understanding. This makes it easier to navigate challenges and ensures everyone is working towards the same goal: the child's success. She stated:

"I think it's being collaborative. We need to collaborate with the parent because they are part of school organization also the schools partnership. All we need to do as a teacher is to build a strong relationship with the parents kay kong wala yan, hindi tayo

magkaintindihan because the good start is building a strong relationship.” (IDI-06)

(I think it is about collaborative. We need to collaborate with the parents because they are part of the school organization, and it is also about the school’s partnership. All we need to do as a teacher is to build a strong relationship with the parents because without that, we would not understand each other. Because the good start is building a strong relationship.)

According to Sexiness (pseudonym), she said that while dealing with overprotective parents can be difficult, teachers need to prioritize patience and adaptability. By ensuring their own actions are well-considered and being open to admitting mistakes even apologizing to parents for missteps, teachers can prevent small issues from escalating. Her statement was:

“Sirugo gyud para sa uban teacher it is not easy gyud to handle overprotective parents no but we have to adjust and extend our patience dapat always tama ang doings ni teacher para wala nay reklamo ang mga ginikanan. Then dili man gyud te perfect as a teacher if atong mali labi nag naa tay nabuhat og na ingon sa ilang anak, mag apologies dayon aron dili na mo dako ang problema ask for their forgiveness ana lang gyud.” (IDI-11)

(For other teachers, dealing with overprotective parents is a really challenging, but we have to adjust and be patient. The teacher’s actions should be correct so that parents have no complaints. As teachers, were not perfect, and if we made a mistake, especially if we say something to their child, we should apologize immediately to avoid escalating the problem and ask their forgiveness, that’s all.)

In addition, Fairy (pseudonym) highlighted about the open communication. Regularly update parents on their child's progress, address their questions calmly and professionally, and avoid actions that might upset them. This builds trust and prevents misunderstandings. Even when you have concerns about a child, approach parents tactfully to work together on solutions, ensuring a positive experience for everyone. As the participant stated that:

“Kong kinahanglan gyud nato sila tagaan pag tagad like update gyud nato sila regards sa performance sailang anak kong naa sila question tubagon nato in a right manner, dili pud nato buhaton ang maka trigger sailang suko bahin sa ilang anak dapat kalma lang ang teacher pirme. Kong ikaw pud teacher naa kay complain sa bata then ask their parents in a right way para walay trouble mahitabo og wala pud bad comments sila saimo.” (IDI-09)

(We really need to give them attention. We should consistently update them regarding their chil’s performance, and if they have questions, we should respond in a proper manner. We should not do anything that might trigger their anger about their child; the teacher should always remain calm. If as a teacher, you have a complaint about a child, ask their parents about it in the right way to avoid any trouble, and so they would not have negative comments about you either.)

The Importance of Communication between Parents, Teacher, and Department of Education

Clear and open communication helps ensure that all parties are informed and aligned on educational goals, policies, and student progress. For teachers, effective communication with parents allows them to better understand a child’s needs, strengths, and challenges, fostering a more personalized approach to instruction. Meanwhile, collaboration with the Department of Education ensures that teachers are following current guidelines and are supported with necessary resources. When these three groups work together, they create a cohesive educational experience that benefits students, promoting academic success and well-being.

Like, Mushroom (pseudonym), one of the informants, highlighted the open communication and investigation before jumping to conclusions. Parents should gather all details before complaining, and teachers must respond promptly. The social media post about an angry teacher using violence is a stark reminder that educators must be mindful of their actions, as careers can be jeopardized by impulsive behavior and the potential for online escalation. She stated like this:

“My suggestion is dapat mag investigate sa sitwasyon ang parent. For example, naa siyag gikasab-an nga bata tapos ni tug-an sa mama/papa unya mo reklamo na unsa man ni siya maam dapat abtik mo response ang teacher kay naa koy nakit an sa facebook nga ang teacher nasuko kay di kabalo mo basa ang bata tuslok siyag ballpen sa bata nag dugo unya ang ginikanan pay nag tug-an sa pulis mag post pa sa social media nga naay teacher kusog mangasaba way pasensya maong makabuhat daw og di maayo ang bata. Labin a sa DepEd kay daghan kaayog bata ang i-handle careful nalang gyud mo sa inyong aksyon even inyong words ky hadlok matanggalan tag trabho tungod ra in ana nga studyante og parent.” (IDI-02)

(My suggestion is that parents should investigate the situation first. For example, if their child tells them something, and then they complain, the teacher should respond promptly. I saw on Facebook that the teacher got angry because the child could not read and that child poked him with a pen, causes bleeding. The parent even went to the police and posted on social media that there is a teacher who yells without patience and that is why the child misbehaved. Especially with the department of education, because there are many children being handled, you should be very careful with your actions and words because we are afraid of losing our jobs because of such student and parents.)

Also, according to Congenial (pseudonym), talks about preventing the misunderstandings and build a strong foundation for learning, schools should consider mandatory parent orientation sessions. These sessions would clarify parents' roles in supporting their child's education within the school environment. By emphasizing collaboration between parents and teachers, these orientations can foster a cooperative spirit that ultimately benefits the child's learning journey. Her statement was:

“Siguro sa DepEd dapat naay parent orientation nga mapasabot sa mga parent sa ilang rule sa ilang mga anak once naan a sa sulod sa school. Kinahanglan man gyud nga ang parent og ang teacher mag collaborate kay para mas mapadali ang pagtudlo sas mga bata, maong kinahanglan gyud ilang cooperation and again dapat well oriented ang mga parents para walay problema.” (IDI-03)

(Perhaps in DepEd, there should be a parent orientation to explain to parents their role in their children’s schooling once they’re inside the school. Both parents and teachers need to collaborate to facilitate the child’s learning, so their cooperation is essential. Again, parents should be well oriented to avoid any issues.)

Furthermore, the statement of Hera (pseudonym) talks about improving student success in public schools, the Department of Education should consider reducing class sizes. Large numbers of students with diverse needs can overwhelm teachers, making it difficult to cater to individual learning styles. By lowering student-teacher ratios, educators could provide more focused attention, leading to a more effective learning environment for all. She stated:

“For the suggestions and recommendation in DepEd I believe those public teachers handle a lot of kids and well all know that learners are diverse and unique they have different. And because of that teacher especially those public teachers had lot numbers of students and encounter struggle and problem in handling their students. Siguro they should lessen the numbers of their students inside of the classroom. For example in a one classroom and half of it is sabtunon ang mga ginikanan tapos ikaw teacher isa lang ka dili na nimo makaya. Probly lessen the numbers of the learners and I think that is my overall suggestion to DepEd.” (IDI-06)

(For the suggestions and recommendations in DepEd, I believe that public school teachers handle a large number of students, and we all know that learners are diverse and unique, with different needs. Because of this, teachers especially those in public schools, often encounter struggles and problem in handling their students. Therefore, they should reduce the number of students in each classroom. For example, if a classroom is supposed to accommodate a certain number of students, and as a teacher, you find it difficult for you to manage all of them. Probably, reducing the number of students would be beneficial. That is my overall suggestion to DepEd.)

Also, the statement of Peace (pseudonym) said that the Department of Education should invest in seminars for both teachers and parents. These workshops could establish clear boundaries and expectations for all parties involved in a child's education. By fostering open communication and understanding of roles, these seminars can help prevent misunderstandings and build a collaborative environment that benefits student learning. She expressed that:

“Akong ma advise sa DepEd maghimo silage seminars para sa mga teachers and parenst. By this makabalo si parent og teacher asa ilang boundary pag-abot sa mga bata para pud ma orient ang tanan og maiwasan ang mga sitwasyon nga dili magkasinabot.” (IDI-08)

(My advice to DepEd is for them to conduct seminars for teachers and parents. Through this, parents and teachers will know their boundaries when it comes to dealing with children, and everyone will be oriented to avoid situation where misunderstanding may arise.)

In addition, Angel (pseudonym) said that the Schools and the Department of Education should address overprotective parents by offering targeted workshops or orientations. These programs could educate parents on appropriate school expectations, fostering a better understanding of student development and the teacher's role. This collaborative approach equips parents with knowledge about what's best for their child's learning within the school environment, reducing anxieties and promoting a more positive dynamic for everyone. As she shared that:

“Ang ako lang ma suggest sa schools and in DepEd is kong naay mga overprotective parents siguro mag orientation sila sa mga parents and mag buat og program para sa mga parents para makabalo sila sa mga dapat og dili dapat sulod sa eskwelahan”. (IDI-12)

(My suggestion to schools and to DepEd is that if there are overprotective parents, they should conduct orientations for parents and create programs to educate them about what should and should not happen within the school.)

Foster Good Association Between School and its Stakeholders

Fostering a good association between the school and its stakeholders involves building strong, positive relationships with all parties involved in the educational process, including students, parents, teachers, staff, and the broader community. This can be achieved through open communication, mutual respect, and active collaboration on common goals. A strong connection with stakeholders helps ensure a supportive learning environment, encourages engagement, and strengthens the overall effectiveness of the school in meeting the needs of its students.

Like the statement of Hera (pseudonym) said that she views parents and children as teammates, not opponents. By approaching them with a friendly and forgiving attitude, you can bridge past misunderstandings. Remember, love for your profession means embracing both students and their parents. As the participant expressed that:

“Instead nga kalabanon na nimo sila you should consider them as your friend. Be friendly at all times, and I believe all those bad things happened before will fade through good communication. Just forget and forgive because you love your job and apil ang bata og ginikanan sa imong profession so that’s it.” (IDI-06)

(Instead of considering them as adversaries, you should regard them as your friends Maintain a friendly attitude at all times, and I

believe that any past misunderstanding. Just let go and forgive because you love your job, and both children and parents are part of your profession.)

Also, the statement of Skye (pseudonym) said that building strong relationships with parents hinges on a foundation of love, respect, and open communication. By genuinely caring for their child, like your own, and demonstrating that care through your interactions, you'll earn their trust. This love, respect, and open communication pave the way for a collaborative environment where everyone feels valued and contributes to the child's success. She stated that:

“To establish a good relationship there should be a love and respect and then good communication sa mga parents. Also learn to love their child kanang murag imoha gyud gikan ang bata kay if makita na sa mga ginikanan nga ge love nato ang ilang anak so diha mag sugod na ilang pagsalig sa atoa.” (IDI 09)

(To establish good relationship, there should be love and respect, along with good communication with the parents. Also, learn to love their child as if they were your own because when parents see that we genuinely care for their child, that's when their trust in us begins)

In addition, the statement of Fiery (pseudonym) talks also about being friendly bond with parents by striking a balance between casual/good conversation and respectful communication. Addressing their children's needs after all, their primary concern is ensuring their child receives proper attention and thrives in school. She stated:

“Make them as your friend be friends to them, communicate with them talk to them casually yet respectful most of the time. Then give the needs of their children kasi yun lang talaga ang gusto nila ang mabigyan pansin ang anak nila sa school.” (IDI-13)

(Make them your friends, be friend to them, communicate with them, talk to them casually yet respectfully most of the time. Then, provide for the needs of their child because that's really what they want for their children to receive attention in school.)

Furthermore, the statement of Passion (pseudonym) tells that some challenging parents are inevitable, remember, staying calm and professional is key. It's part of the job. By respectfully addressing them with a smile, you can help them feel at ease, opening the door for a more productive conversation. She stated:

“As what I've always do is kalmado lang all the time, learn to accept nga naa gyud mga in ana nga parents it is normal and it is your job as a teacher to deal it. Also, if magkita mo tagdon nimo tapos og mangutana response with respect and smile to them, para comfortable sila saimoha.” (IDI-10)

(As I always do, I remain calm all the times and learn to accept that there are indeed parents like that. It is normal, and it is your job as a teacher to deal with it. Also, if you meet them, address them and respond respectfully and with a smile, so they feel comfortable with you.)

In addition, Sexiness (pseudonym) said that the maintaining a respectful and approachable demeanor towards parents is crucial. Remember, they're invested in the school's success too. A friendly smile goes a long way in building rapport and showing them, you value their presence as partners in their child's education. She stated:

“Tagdon gyud natog tarong ang mga parents with respect kay apil man gyud na sila diri sa school stakeholder's pud biya na sila. Kong Kinahanglan mo smile ka every time magkita mo sa school then do it para ganahan ang parents saimo.” (IDI-11)

(Always address the parents with respect because they are also part of the school as a stakeholder. If you need to, smile every time you see them at school in order for the parents to appreciate you.)

Conclusions

The meticulous analysis conducted in this phenomenological study provides invaluable experience insights and recommendations of private elementary teachers with regards in dealing with overprotective parents. It illuminates how these educators navigate the challenges and difficulties in dealing students and their parents, also their strategies were being used to cope up upon their struggles and also, they shared their suggestions upon this overparenting. As the facilitator of this study, it was essential to acknowledge and bolster their resilience through the use of relevant, valid, and balanced methodologies aimed at supporting their morale and efficacy in the classroom.

Furthermore, beyond data collection, our responsibility as researchers extends to treating participants with utmost respect and safeguarding their entrusted personal data to ensure research integrity. This study not only contributes to the ongoing discourse surrounding educational reform but also serves as a guide for future elementary educators, emphasizing the dynamic nature of success and the importance of patience and strong relationship within the school. By delving into the experience and insights of elementary teachers, this research seeks to establish a strong relationship within the teacher-parent, enriching student's needs and a better understanding for teachers about this kind of parents that they might encounter.

Reflecting on the limitations highlighted earlier in this paper, it is worth noting that the study was specifically designed to share some experience related to the overprotective parents they encounter in elementary school, without claiming to provide a comprehensive representation of all such elementary teachers. Specifically, the research focused on 14 elementary teachers in different private

elementary schools in Maniki, Kapalong Davao del Norte. This limitation underscores that our study may not wholly capture the different experience, insights of other elementary teachers. Therefore, the research topic is ripe for further exploration and validation in future studies.

There is significant room for modification in future research endeavors. Alterations could be made in the research approach, the participant selection, and the scope of the study to validate and substantiate the findings of this study. The research approach, in particular, could be adapted based on emerging needs or new research questions. Thus, future researchers are encouraged to reproduce, augment, or even challenge this study, applying their discretion and expertise in their approach.

Further studies could also incorporate additional follow-up interviews with the same informants to track any changes in their insights and thoughts over time. This longitudinal approach could provide a dynamic experience on the elementary teachers and shed light on how their insights evolve as they continue their efforts towards serving the students and their parents.

Lastly, by delving deeper into these areas, researcher's can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities surrounding helicopter parenting in the elementary school setting. This research can equip educators and parents with valuable tools to nurture a positive and productive learning environment for all students.

References

Addi-Raccah, A., & Grinshtain, Y. (2021). Teachers Professionalism and relation with parents: teacher and parents view. *Research Papers in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2021.1931949>.

Addi-Raccah, A., Grinshtain, Y. (2021). Teachers' professionalism and relations with parents: teachers' and parents' views. *Research papers in education*, 37(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2021.1931949>

Arslan, B., Lucassen N., Keijsers L, Stevens GWJM. When Too Much Help is of No Help: Mothers' and Fathers' Perceived Overprotective Behavior and (Mal)Adaptive Functioning in Adolescents. *J Youth Adolesc*. 2023 May;52(5):1010-1023. doi: 10.1007/s10964-022-01723-0. Epub 2023 Jan 12. PMID: 36633796; PMCID: PMC10027782.

Alomes, B. (2023) The Importance of Stakeholders When it Comes to Creating Successful Learning Outcomes: Natural Pod. [Naturalpod.com/the-importance-of-stakeholders-when-it-comes-to-creating-successful-learning-outcomes/](https://www.naturalpod.com/the-importance-of-stakeholders-when-it-comes-to-creating-successful-learning-outcomes/)

Amand, J. (2022) Epirical Validation of a Model for Predicting Students Sense of Belonging and School Engagement as a Function of Classroom Management Practices: *International Journal of Education Psychology*. eric.ed.gov/?q=the+effectiveness+of+school+and+classroom+rules+implementation+&id+EJ1355282

Angert, J. (2020) The Impact of Parenting in Secondary Education: Northern Central University ProQuest Dissertation. <https://proquest.com/openview/e4ecf082a7e94f8541a36d54e8a82?d8/L?pq-origsite=scholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>

Aprianti, W., Muslihin, H. Y., & Elan, E. (2021). Applying discipline character: Parents vs. teachers. *Journal of Early Childhood Care and Education*, 4(1), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.26555/jecce.v4i1.4004>

Arslan, P., & Kiral, B. (2022) Elementary School Teachers Experience with Overprotective/helicopter: *Ankara University Journal of Faculty of Educational Sciences*, 55(3). <https://doi.org/10.30964/auebfd.1035605>

Barger, M (2019) The Relationship Between Parent's Involvement in Children's Schooling and Children's Adjustment: A Meta Analysis, 45(9). <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul000201>

Bridges, D. (2021) The Importance of Patience in the Classroom: *National Heritage Academies*. [Nhaschools.com/enblog/Teachers-Lounge/The-Importance-of-Patience-in-the-Classroom](https://www.nhaschools.com/enblog/Teachers-Lounge/The-Importance-of-Patience-in-the-Classroom)

Casey, A. (2022) Parental Involvement in your Children's Education. The Key to Students Success, Research Shows. <https://www.aecf.org/blog/parental-involvement-is-key-to-student-success-research-shows>

Costa, R., Oliveira, A. (2019). GATE Teachers from the inside out: students' perception on gifted and talented teachers in the classroom. *Identifying, describing and teachers*, 6(20). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5879-8.ch020>

Cruzat, M., Javillonar, M. (2022) The school and its stakeholders: partnership in building a strong school community: *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*. [Allmultidisciplinaryjournal.com/uploads/archieves/20220812155658_D-22-74.1.pdf](https://www.allmultidisciplinaryjournal.com/uploads/archieves/20220812155658_D-22-74.1.pdf)

Cuzzocrea F. (2019). The six dimensions of parenting and adolescent psychological adjustment: The mediating role of psychological needs. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 60(2), 128–137. 10.1111/sjop.12507.

Dabell, J. (2020) Dealing with A Complaint: Everyday is a school. [johndabell.com/2020/01/27/dealing-with-a-complaint](https://www.johndabell.com/2020/01/27/dealing-with-a-complaint)

Epstein, J. (2019). Framework of Six Types of Involvement. *Organizing Engagement*. <https://organizingengagement.com>.

org/models/framework-of-six-types-of-involvement/

Escobal, C., Ann, J., Sarah M., Arboleda, F. (2023) Philippine Public School Values Education Teachers' Experience in Classroom Positive Discipline: A Phenomenological Inquiry Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal Philippine Public School Values Education Teachers' Experiences in Classroom Positive Discipline: A Phenomenological Inquiry. Psychology in education, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305107>

Fisher, Y., & Fanyo R. (2022). Parents perception of teacher' authority and parental involvement: The impact of communality. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13(9). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.908290>

Foster, S. (2022, February 7) Classroom Management for learning: Center for Teaching & Learning. <https://www.colorado.edu/center/teaching-learning/2022/02/07/classroom-management-learning>

Ganly, S. (2021) Gordon's Theory of Discipline in Classroom. Medium <https://sarahganly1.medium.com/gordons-theories-on-discipline-in-the-classroom-84a6cd8b2d9d>

Gil, E., & Ginanto, D (2023) International Parents Navigating Parental Involvement in a U.S International Parents Navigating Parental Involvement. ResearchGate, (9)5. <https://doi.org/10.5422/jmer.2022-2023.v12.57-82>

Guskey, T., & Kwang, S. (2019). What Works in Professional Development? The Leading Edge: Professional Learning. <https://tguskey.com/wp-content/uploads/Professional-Learning-5-What-Works-in-Professional-Development.pdf>

Han, C., & Masse L. (2022). Parental Autonomy Support in the Context of Parent-Child Negotiation for Children's Independent Mobility: I Always Feel Sfer with my Parents to Boom! Bust Down Those Walls!: The Jorney of Early Adolescence, 42(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/02724316211064513>

Hampton, L., & Rodriquez. E. (2022) Building Effective Partnerships with Prents to Support Language Development in Young Children. *Intervention in School and Clinic*. <https://doi.org/10.1177?10534512221081260>

Jackson, A. (2018). Parental involvement as a Important Factor for Successful Education. *C.E.P.S Jounal Vol.7*. files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1156936.pdf

Krugel, M. (2019). Teachers response to helicopter parents whose children experience barriers to learning: University of Johnnesburg. <https://hdl.handle.net/10210/446230>

Kumar, A. (2022). Why Parents-Teachers Communication is Important? LeadSchool. <https://leadschool.in/blog/why-parent-teacher-communication-is-important/>

Labo, N. (2019). Enhancing School-Home Communication Through Learning Managent System Adoption: Parents and Teachers Perceptions and Practices. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1219893.pdf>

Lin, S. (2019). Uncovering a Connection between the Teachers Professional Development Progra and Students Learning: *Journal of education and practice*. eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1079018.pdf

Lyons, S. (2021, January 28). Are you overparenting: Favorite online S.T.E.M resources.<https://kcparent.com/parenting/are-you-overparenting/#:~:text=According%20to%20the%20Cambridge%20Dictionary,beyond%20with%20basic%20tasks%2C%20commo>

Mgaiwa, E. (2018) Teachers Feelings about the Status of the Teaching Profession and Associated Factors in Tanzania. *Journal of Teacher Education and educators*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1402350.pdf>

Mondal, G., & Roy, J. (2019). Teaching Proffession and Educational Accountability in Tanzania. Under a Creative Commons License. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e0761>

Motete, R. (2021). Teaching profession and educational accountability in Tanzania. [ScienceDirect.Sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S20584402101714X#bib](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S20584402101714X#bib)

Nordin, M., & Bortolome M. (2018). Parental Involvement in the Philippines. A review of literature (6)5. <https://doi.org/10.37134/Saej>

Pedro, C., & Sannadan D. (2020) Analysis of School Conflicts Involving Parents: Experiences and resolution: *Jurnal Inovatif Ilmu Pendidikan* (2)2. <https://doi.org/10.23960/jiip.v2i2.21817>

Prateek, y., & Omna, S (2022). Helicopter parenting, from good intentions to poor outcome. *Journal of Family Mediicine and Primary Care*. [hptts://doi.org/10.4103?jfmpe.jfmpe_2474_21](https://doi.org/10.4103?jfmpe.jfmpe_2474_21)

Rodriquez, B. (2023). Classroom Rules: Importance and Tips for Creating and Enforcing Them. *Public School Works*. <https://corp.publicschoolworks.com/resource/classroom-rules-importance-and-tips-for-creating-and-enforcing-them/>

Salim, R. (2023). Uncertainly Reduction Strategies for Parents of day care service users. *Researchgate*,(4)2.

<https://doi.org/10.35760/dimedcom.2023.v2i2.9922>

Santana, M. (2018). Parents and Teachers working together to enhance students success in the classroom. Digital Commons@CSUMB. [Digitalcommons.csumb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1408&context=caps](https://digitalcommons.csumb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1408&context=caps)

Seeley, H. (2019). Enhancing School-Home Communication Through Learning Managent System Adoption: Parents and Teachers Perceptions and Practices. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1219893.pdf>

Sholeh, A. (2022) Teachers Interpersonal Communication Patterns in Improving the Quality of Education Learning. *Journal Pendidikan*. <https://journal.staihubbulwathan.id/index.php/alishlah/article/download/1460/1233>

Smith, J. (2022). Epirical Validation of a Model for Predicting Students Sense of Belonging and School Engagement as a Function of Classroom Management Practices: *International Journal of Education Psychology*. eric.ed.gov/?q=the+effectiveness+of+school+and+classroom+rules+implementation+&id=EJ1355282

Villamarin, A. (2023) Proposal:Parental Complaints/Feedback Policy and Procedures. *Researchgate*,(7)4. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.216349.18400>

Vira, E. (2021). International Parents Navigating Parental Involvement in a U.S School: a Call for International Responsive Schools. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1398939.pdf>

Westpharen, D., & Arzt, N (2023) Overprotective Parents: Signs, Example, & Effect s on Mental Health. *Choosing Theraphy* [https://www.choosingtherapy.com/overprotective-parents/#:~:text=There%20are%20advantages%20associated%](https://www.choosingtherapy.com/overprotective-parents/#:~:text=There%20are%20advantages%20associated%20)

Withs, A (2023). Enchancing Prent-School Partnership Through a General Parents Orientation Program. *GEO Academic Journal*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.56738/issn29603986.geo2023.4.42>

Yael, S., & Rodriquez, E (2023). Building Effective Partnership with Prents to Support Language Development in Young Children: Intervntion in School and Clinic. eric.ed.gov/?q=effective+strategies+to+deal+with+parents&id=EJ1359213

Yu, G., & Wang, C. (20 IL23). Teacher as mediator: How teacher Interacts with parents of the victim and agent in school conflict. *Contrastive pragmatics*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1163/26660393-bja10070>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Cristina V. Sugarol

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Deveyvon L. Espinosa, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines